

Research

Investment Attractiveness of Renewable Energies

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Abstract: Optimum economic sustainability and national grid-parity of renewable energies require significant investment attractiveness (IA) for the feasibility of proposed power generation projects. Using Investment benefit analysis method; this paper aims to identify a method to determine the IA of renewable energy project at a solar power plant (SPP) in Bangladesh. Data was analyzed using two modeling-software: RETScreen-Expert analyses and Microsoft excel along with Discounted-Cash-flow (DCF) model; which displayed differences in annual-costs. The results illustrate that each of six used parameters has the potential to influence all economic tools, except electricity sales via LCOE calculation. The sensitivity range ($\pm 25\%$) NPV attests Electricity-Exported to the Grid to be the most sensitive measure, followed by Initial-Capital-Investment (ICI). Any changes made to optimize the photovoltaic (PV) tilt-angle, influenced maximum rate of the capacity factor for the SPP. Furthermore, LCOE is the most salient factor influencing increased NPV, followed by ICI. In conclusion, the study emphasizes the assessment of underlying uncertainty in a new project's costs and power generation. Moreover, it clarifies that the economic tools and methodologies herein can establish benchmark models useful for the implementation of other projects, especially those focusing on doubt surrounding IA.

Keywords: Investment attractiveness (IA); Renewable energy; Net Present Value (NPV); Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Discounted Payback Period (DPP); Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE).

1. Introduction

Since the advent of more rigorous global climate change agreements, many nations are turning to new, safer and cleaner sources of energy production. Nevertheless, there are a large number of

geographical regions, one example being Bangladesh, that face increasing population density, yet significant power shortages, regardless of the production source [1] [2]. It is therefore very advantageous for economically underdeveloped regions to use their potential energy resources in an economically viable manner, yet one which is environmentally friendly.

According to the World Bank statistics, the population density of Bangladesh in 2018 was 1240 people / km²; and in that year, the 10th most populous country in the world in terms of density [3]. Bangladesh has a domestic power penetration rate of 90% [1], however, there is still a supply-demand gap. The country is thus, turning to its relatively abundant renewable energy sources such as solar and wind energy, which have great potential for development. Although vigorously developing renewable energy for power generation could potentially alleviate the supply-gap dilemma, a current problem is the lack of investment in renewable energy projects [4]. The focus of current research, therefore, is to verify the feasibility of renewable energy power generation so that investors know their economic risk ahead of time.

In Bangladesh, electricity is the key to economic growth. The region's natural gas supply accounts for 57.5% of power generation, coal power provides 2.95% and oil power 22.73%. Power generation, therefore, mainly depends on natural gas. Bangladesh, however, currently faces a shortage of 1 billion cubic feet of natural gas per day [5]. Therefore, the development of renewable energy plays an important role in accelerating the industrialization process and improving the power supply of Bangladesh. Due to the geographical location of Bangladesh, the country receives an average of 4-6.5 kWh / m² of solar radiation per day (Table 3), which can generate 1018×10^{18} J energy [2], hence solar power generation has great potential. Using the Teknaf solar power plant in Bangladesh as an example, this paper also demonstrates the feasibility of investment in solar power projects to promote power generation and provides a reference for other countries with regard to renewable energy investment issues.

In the existing research, the main methods used to evaluate the investment feasibility of renewable energy power generation projects were investment benefit analysis, Monte Carlo simulation analysis and real option analysis. In the past, however, most of the literature only measured the feasibility of the project from the perspective of economics, lacking the overall evaluation of the project [6] [7] [8]. Due to the fact that the investment benefit analysis is based on known variable relationships to analyze the economic index, a good way to evaluate the project scheme is with RETScreen expert, a software tool based on intelligent decision making. It can rapidly analyze

and identify issues in decision making pertinent to clean energy [9] [10]. In order to overcome the shortcomings of the previous literature, this paper makes a comprehensive analysis of Teknaf solar power plant from the perspectives of economy, environment and risk and establishes a benchmark model to evaluate the investment feasibility of renewable energy power generation projects. First, the data of Teknaf solar power plant are analyzed quantitatively by RETScreen expert, with economic indexes such as mention net present value (NPV), discounted payback period (DPP) and Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE). Secondly, an environmental impact assessment is carried out by comparing the CO₂ emissions of solar power generation and crude oil power generation. Third, the risk range of the parameters is limited to $\pm 25\%$, with emphasis on assessing the potential uncertainty of the cost and expected cash flow of power generation by the solar power project. Finally, sensitivity analysis is used to determine whether the investment itself, is an important variable in assessing the Energy potential of the solar power project.

2. Literature review

2.1 Evaluation index of project economy

Economic evaluation indexes of investment projects are classified by time value, including static evaluation indexes and dynamic evaluation indexes. In the evaluation of investment projects, dynamic evaluation index is the main method, while static evaluation index is the auxiliary method. Due to the fact that the static evaluation index does not consider the time value of funds, it can affect rationality principles, and therefore can often have a negative impact on investment decision-making. The dynamic evaluation index is based on cash flow and introduces the time value of money, which greatly enhances the analysis of factors in investment decision-making. At present, the economic indicators to evaluate the feasibility of project investment mainly include static investment payback period (IPP), net present value (NPV) and internal rate of return (IRR). As for the selection of these indicators, Duan [11] gave a detailed explanation on the selection of economic evaluation indicators in investment projects. In addition, for power supply systems, the common index is the levelized power cost, and in feasibility studies of renewable energy projects, a number of documents have used NPV, IRR, DPP and LCOE as indicators. For example, Dalton et al [12] used wave height (HS) and period (T) data to estimate the annual energy output of wave energy converters in multiple countries, and estimated the power cost, NPV and internal rate of return (IRR) based on various Input parameters. Luigi Dusonchet et al [13] conducted an economic analysis on the main supporting mechanisms of PV technology in EU countries via NPV and IRR.

Do Truong et al [14] conducted economic analysis on bioethanol according to investment payback period (IPP), investment return rate and product value.

2.2 Measurement method of project economic index

According to existing research, this paper suggests that Monte Carlo simulation, real option analysis and investment benefit analysis are the three main methods to measure the economic indicators of project investment feasibility. Monte Carlo simulation is a widely used method to study the uncertainty in a probabilistic way. For example, Giancarlo Aquila et al [7] used Monte Carlo method to simulate the monthly power generation of the Brazilian electric power market stroke field over 20 years, including uncertainty in variables, and they calculated its (NPV). Luiz Célio Souza Rocha et al [8] used Monte Carlo simulation to simulate the Brazilian residential wind power project 10000 times, and obtained the possible NPV of the project, which proved its stochastic economic feasibility. The Monte Carlo simulation method, however, has its inherent shortcomings. The value of each uncertainty factor is completely random, which may ignore the relationship between the uncertainty factors, and thus can factor into the accuracy of analytic results. Real option analysis on the other hand, is an accurate method to predict the value of strategic investment, and is increasingly becoming a key management tool in unstable economic environments. Martínez-Cesena et al [15] proposed an advanced real option analysis for renewable energy power generation project planning, and illustrated the method with a case study of hydropower stations. Bauner et al [16] used the option value framework to study household investment in solar PV power, and considering the impact of delayed investment on uncertainty. Using the Monte Carlo simulation model, the optimal adoption time, the critical value of discounted income and the adoption rate were determined by these authors. There are, however, some deficiencies in the use of real options to evaluate the value of the project. First of all, it is difficult to define and confirm the real option. Secondly, it needs to meet many assumptions to determine the value of the option, making it a less practical evaluation method.

Investment benefit analysis, is used to evaluate the project from an economic point of view. For example, Hoque et al [17] used the investment benefit analysis method to analyze the long-term benefits of solar power generation in Bangladesh, and to obtain the return period and NPV of solar power system investment. Ivonne Peña et al [18] conducted an annual analysis of wind power plants in Portugal from 1992 to 2010, and obtained the net income of independent wind power

producers to show their investment benefits. Kabyanga et al [19] analyzed the investment benefit of experimental households and non-biogas households in central Uganda, and conducted sensitivity analysis to measure the financial feasibility of investment cost reduction. MD Tasbirul Islam et al [20] [21] evaluated Malaysia's centralized solar power generation (CSP) technology through investment benefit analysis, and used sensitivity analysis to investigate the impact of levelized power cost on various project discount rates. Nevertheless, the above scholars only analyzed the economic benefits and there was a lack of overall evaluation of the projects, while some scholars introduce risk analysis on the basis of investment benefit analysis. For example, Lin et al [22] calculated the net present value, investment payback period and internal income of solar power projects in Taiwan, and carried out sensitivity analysis, therefore assisting investors with a given guaranteed price. They also evaluated and analyzed expected benefits and potential risks. Bustos et al [23] evaluated the NPV and IRR of solar power plants and conducted risk analysis.

In addition, with the increasingly prominent environmental problems, other scholars regard carbon emission reduction as the evaluation index of energy investment projects. For example, Sepideh Sadat Korsavi et al [24] studied the economic performance and environmental benefits of 14 roof PV systems in Iran, and evaluated the NPV, investment payback period IPP, IRR and levelized power cost as well as CO₂ emissions. Alexander et al [25] Investigated alternative rice production systems with different residual management schemes in northern Vietnam, and calculated the NPV differences between different production systems by respectively considering the greenhouse gas emission reduction under the low carbon and high carbon price scenarios.

This paper, chose the investment benefit analysis as the method to measure the investment feasibility of renewable energy projects. However, most of the existing studies only use the investment benefit analysis to evaluate the investment feasibility of renewable energy power generation projects, or introduce the environment or risk assessment on this basis. In this paper, the investment benefit analysis is used to analyze teknaf solar power plant from the perspectives of economy, environment and risk, and a model for evaluating the investment feasibility of renewable energy power generation projects is established Type.

Table 1 Contribution from other findings

Author	(IA)	RE	Investment benefit analysis	Energy policy
Md. Abdullah Hil Baky et al [2]	*	*		*
R. A. Barreto [4]		*		*

F. Amri [6]		*		*
Aquila et al [7]		*		*
Luiz Célio Souza Rocha et al [8]	*	*	*	
Saiful Islam et al [9]	*	*		*
Roberto De Lieto Vollaro et al [10]	*	*	*	
D. Yu [11]	*	*	*	
G.J. Dalton et al [12]	*	*	*	
Luigi Dusonchet et al [13]	*	*	*	*
Do Truong et al [14]	*	*	*	
Eduardo Alejandro Martinez Cesena et al [15]	*	*	*	*
Bauner et al [16]	*	*	*	*
Najmul Hoque et al [17]	*	*	*	
Ivonne Peña et al [18]	*	*	*	*
Kabyanga et al [19]	*	*	*	
Islam et al [20]	*	*	*	*
Rosnani Binti Affandi et al [21]	*	*	*	*
H.-F lin, Z.-H Wang [22]	*	*	*	*
F. Bustos et al [23]	*	*	*	
Sepideh Sadat Korsavi et al [24]	*	*	*	
Alexander M. Stuart et al [25]	*	*	*	
T.M.I. Mahlia et al [26]	*	*	*	
Kenji Shiraishi et al [27]	*	*	*	*
This paper	*	*	*	*

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Methods and data

The purpose of this paper is to measure and evaluate the investment feasibility of Teknaf solar power plant, a renewable energy power generation project. The paper uses RETScreen expert to analyze the investment benefit, calculate the net cash value over time, IRR, DPP, and levelized power cost, in addition to assessing risk analysis and conducting an environmental impact analysis. Hence, the current investment feasibility of Teknaf solar power plant is evaluated from multiple perspectives.

3.2 Investment benefit analysis method

3.2.1 Net present value (NPV)

NPV is the sum of the present value of the net cash flow in the evaluation period, calculated according to the benchmark yield of the project, and it is a dynamic evaluation index to inspect the profitability of the project in the evaluation period. Investors can obtain NPV through cash flow

in different periods, so NPV can reflect the time value of money. NPV is a useful tool to identify the economic feasibility of a project. When NPV is negative or relatively small, the project is not economically feasible; when NPV is positive, the project is considered economically feasible. Investors can then decide whether to invest in the project. NPV is a type of index to compare the economic value and feasibility of a project, but the discount rate adopted is not easily determined, so it needs to be assumed.

$PVA > 0$: then the project is profitable

$PVA < 0$: the project is not profitable.

Steps:

- Collect annual income data from electricity sales and operation costs.
- Discount the cash flow to find the present value (PrV)
- Sum the PrVs and take away the initial investment to get the NPV.

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \left[C_t / (1+r)^t \right] - C_o$$

Equation 1

C_t : Cash inflow for the time-period;

C_o : Total initial investment costs;

r : Discount rate

t : Number of periods

3.2.2 Internal Rate of Return (IRR)

IRR is the discount rate when the total present value of capital inflow is equal to the total present value of capital outflow and the NPV is zero. Generally, the project is feasible when the IRR is greater than or equal to the benchmark rate of return (discount rate). The value range of the IRR should be $0 < IRR < \infty$, and the IRR obtained should be compared with the set benchmark rate of return (R) of the project. When $IRR \geq R$, it indicates that the rate of return of the project has reached or exceeded the level of the set discount rate. The project is then feasible, and can be considered to be acceptable. IRR reflects the efficiency of investment, and its outstanding advantage is that it does not need to give the benchmark discount rate in advance.

$$\sum_{t=1}^T [C_t / (1 + irr)^t] - C_0 = 0$$

Equation 2

Ct: Cash inflow for the time-period;

Co: Total initial investment costs;

irr: Internal rate of return

t: Number of periods

3.2.3 Discounted payback period (DPP)

The DPP discounts any future net cash flow caused by the investment. The payback period is the time it takes to break even from undertaking the initial investment. It is a sign of zero cost. Different from the simple payback period (SPP), the DPP considers the time value of money. In addition, the SPP does not consider the discount rate, which will affect the time of fund recovery. For example, if the SPP is 4 and the PV life is 20 years, then we will get free electricity within 16 years [26]. This paper, therefore, chooses DPP as the index of investment.

3.2.4 Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)

LCOE is the value of comparing the cost of one power generation mode with another or one power plant with another [27] [28]. If LCOE is lower or equal to the current Energy price, the technology is marketable [29]. Its purpose is to compare the cost of renewable energy technology with the energy price of the power grid, and then determine whether it can achieve parity access to the power grid. This is the only calculation that has nothing to do with income. All annual operating and maintenance costs are discounted and aggregated into the initial investment, resulting in total production costs. This cost is divided by the total Energy expected to be produced in 20 years. Equation 3 shows the method for calculating LCOE. The required data are namely, capital investment, annual operation and maintenance cost of Energy, electricity exported to the grid and annual effective discount rate (R).

$$LCOE = \left(C_0 + \sum_{t=1}^T AOM_t / (1+r)^t \right) / \sum_{t=1}^T AEP_t / (1+r)^t$$

Equation 3

Co: Total initial investment cost

AOMt: Annual Operation & maintenance cost for a period of time

AEP: Annual energy production for a period of time

r: discount rate.

3.3 Data model

Teknaf solar power plant is located in Teknaf, Cox Bazar District, Chittagong City Branch, Bangladesh, with a geographical location of 20.90 degrees North latitude, 92.30 degrees east longitude, an altitude of 92 meters, and an annual average wind speed of 2.4 meters / second. The climate in this area is similar to other areas of Bangladesh, with the characteristics of tropical monsoon weather and coastal wind. The monthly average temperature of the power plant is above 18 °C, and the annual average temperature is 26.1 °C. With regard to heat, the hottest month is May, with an average temperature of 28.7 °C; the coldest month being January, with an average temperature of 21.2 °C. The annual average precipitation in the region of Teknaf power plant is 3954.8mm, and the month with the most precipitation is July, with an average precipitation of 1028.7mm. January has the least precipitation, with an average of 2.5mm of rainfall.

Teknaf started with a debt ratio of 50% and debt term of 15 years, and the power plant's proposition is to have 20 years of lifetime [30] [31]. Teknaf power plant has a power capacity of 28MW and is capable of releasing a further 20MW. The plant has 87500 Mono-Si-JAM6-72-320/SI solar PV panels installed and operating and the expected annual yield of power from the plant is 43000-Megawatt hours (MWh) [31] [30]. The total initial cost is BD Tk 300 Crore, which is equivalent to 47430000 Canadian Dollar (CAD) According to Teknaf Solateck Ltd., the generated electricity is sold to the Bangladesh Power Development Board (BPDB) at 0.17CAD.

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 Excel spreadsheet Scenario analysis

Following the context of the financial approaches in Investment benefit analysis method, this analysis proceeded to test if Teknaf would be cost beneficial over 20 years. By referring to (Table 2) the NPV turns out to be greater than zero (\$15,976,878.22 CAD), IRR equivalent to 13% and a DPP of 11.07 years, this project is likely to be beneficial. Remarkably, as the value of the cash flow in the present study becomes higher, the sooner the payback period is approached and IRR gets greater than the discount rate (9%). This realization could justify a sustainable power

generation system although socio-economic sustainability also needs to be accounted for, particularly in new power project development and implementation. This exact fact should push investors to examine the production cost and compare with the usual grid price or any other power generation system affordable to the society. Conferring to (Table 2) the levelized cost is lower than the grid price by CAD 0.053 equivalent to 3.5 BD Tk. The discounted rate effect (9%) on cash flow could be to influence the yielded NPV, or can be accounted as a delaying factor of Payback period. In other words, a profitable energy generation project should be able to succeed in current and future economic situations, to conveniently contribute to the economic growth of a country.

Table 2 Economic approaches calculated in Excel

Time	O&M	Cost PV	Revenue	Cash flows	PV CF	cumulative CF	AEP (PV) kWh	AEP (kWh)	4.30E+07
0		(\$47,430,000.00)		(\$47,430,000.00)	(\$47,430,000.00)	(\$47,430,000)	43000000	AOM	\$364,000.00
1	-364000	(\$333,944.95)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$6,372,477.06	(\$41,057,523)	39449541.28	Co	\$47,430,000.00
2	-364000	(\$306,371.52)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$5,846,309.23	(\$35,211,214)	36192239.71	R	9%
3	-364000	(\$281,074.79)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$5,363,586.45	(\$29,847,627)	33203889.64	NPV	<u>\$15,976,878.22</u>
4	-364000	(\$257,866.78)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$4,920,721.52	(\$24,926,906)	30462284.08	DPP (years)	<u>11.07</u>
5	-364000	(\$236,575.02)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$4,514,423.41	(\$20,412,482)	27947049.61	IRR	13%
6	-364000	(\$217,041.31)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$4,141,672.85	(\$16,270,809)	25639495.06	Grid price	0.17 \$/kWh
7	-364000	(\$199,120.47)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$3,799,699.86	(\$12,471,110)	23522472.53	LCOE (\$/kWh)	<u>0.117</u>
8	-364000	(\$182,679.33)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$3,485,963.18	(\$8,985,146)	21580250.03		
9	-364000	(\$167,595.71)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$3,198,131.36	(\$5,787,015)	19798394.52		
10	-364000	(\$153,757.53)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$2,934,065.46	(\$2,852,950)	18163664.7		
11	-364000	(\$141,061.96)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$2,691,803.18	(\$161,146)	16663912.57		
12	-364000	(\$129,414.64)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$2,469,544.20	\$2,308,398	15287993.18		
13	-364000	(\$118,729.03)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$2,265,636.88	\$4,574,035	14025681.82		
14	-364000	(\$108,925.71)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$2,078,565.95	\$6,652,601	12867598		
15	-364000	(\$99,931.85)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$1,906,941.23	\$8,559,542	11805135.78		
16	-364000	(\$91,680.59)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$1,749,487.37	\$10,309,029	10830399.79		
17	-364000	(\$84,110.64)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$1,605,034.29	\$11,914,063	9936146.601		

18	-364000	(\$77,165.72)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$1,472,508.52	\$13,386,572	9115730.826		
19	-364000	(\$70,794.24)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$1,350,925.25	\$14,737,497	8363055.804		
20	-364000	(\$64,948.84)	7310000	\$6,946,000.00	\$1,239,380.96	\$15,976,878	7672528.261		
		(\$50,752,790.63)		13%	\$15,976,878.22		\$435,527,463.79		

4.2 Location and Climate assessment

The analysis used geographical location and climate data from the location of the facility. Table 3 and Figure 1 show a description of climate data over a year. The facilities geographical location and climate data show that the annual average of daily solar radiation equals to 4.69kWh/d and the annual air temperature is 25.6°. Daily solar radiation is distributed in three ranges: From February to May there is a notable gain in solar radiation 5.32, 5.84, 5.92, 5.31) kWh/day this contrast to other remaining parts of the year. The period of June to August ranges (3.86, 3.81, and 3.95) kWh and the period from September to January marks a moderate daily solar radiation distribution (4.25, 4.4, 4.34, 4.48, and 4.48) kWh/day. As a country characterized by different seasons, it appears that tilt angles could change seasonally [32]. Simulation with RETScreen used a tilt angle equivalent to the local latitude of the selected facility to find the annual energy yield to the power grid. It makes an increment rate (5%) to that of the horizontal surface which is worth 5% of annual energy exported to the grid “latitude (tilt=20.9): 43537mWh, Horizontal (tilt=0): 41178mWh”

Table 3 Climate data over a year at the geographical location of Teknaf

Month	Air temperature	Relative humidity	Precipitation	Daily-solar radiation-horizontal	Atmospheric pressure	Wind speed	Earth temperature
	°C	%	mm	kWh/m ² /d	kPa	m/s	°C
January	20.3	57.3%	2.79	4.8	100.3	2.6	20.8
February	22.7	55.2%	9.8	5.32	100.2	2.3	22.8
March	25.9	60.60%	21.3	5.84	100	2.1	26
April	27.9	67.70%	62.1	5.92	99.8	2	28.2
May	28.5	75.20%	230.02	5.31	99.5	2.4	28.8
June	28	84.20%	399.3	3.86	99.2	3.1	28.3
July	27.3	87.80%	516.46	3.81	99.3	3.2	27.5
August	27.1	88.10%	413.23	3.95	99.3	2.8	27.3
September	27.1	86.60%	234.9	4.25	99.6	2.2	27.4

October	26.7	81.20%	141.36	4.4	99.9	2	27.2
November	24.4	73.10%	32.7	4.34	100.2	2.2	24.9
December	21.2	66.30%	6.51	4.48	100.4	2.3	21.8
Annual	25.59	73.6%	2070.47	4.69	99.8	2.4	25.9
Source	NASA	NASA	NASA	NASA	NASA	NASA	NASA

Figure 1 Climate data at Teknaf over a year showing daily solar radiation and air temperature.

Table 4 Annual O&M (AOM) provided in RETScreen Expert database

Technology	Power plant – O&M costs – Typical (&/kw-year)					
	10kW	100kW	1000kW	10000 kW	100000kW	1000000kW
Photovoltaic	33	25	18	<u>13</u>	10	8
Photovoltaic – Tracking system	41	30	22	17	12	10

4.3 Energy Production and Financial viability

RETScreen Expert reveals the impact of capacity factor and tilt angle at Teknaf solar power plant. Optimization of tilt angle ensures the maximum energy generation, thereby lowering the power generation cost [33]. Any change made to optimize the tilt angle influences the capacity factor to the maximum operating rates for each solar power generating technology (Table 5). Annual cost divides into two different parts: Annual Operation and Maintenance Cost (AOM) and annual debt payment cost [34] [35]. This study used the AOM provided in RETScreen Expert database (Table 4) and a debt ratio of 50% paid over 15 years (free of taxes). The total savings and annual costs

yield a net yearly cash flow of CAD 5365000 (Table 6) which is equivalent to BD Tk 34 Crore in Bangladeshi currency [30].

Table 5 Energy and Financial Data Entry and Processing on PV Tilt Angle

Solar tracking system	Solar tracking system	Fixed
	Tilt angle	20.9°
	Azimuth	0°
Photovoltaic	Type	Mono-Si
	Power capacity	28000 kw
	Manufacturer	JA Solar
	Model	Mono-Si-JAM-72-320/SI
	Number of units	87500
	Efficiency	16.51%
	Nominal operating cell temperature	45°C
	Temperature coefficient	0.4%/ °C
	Solar collector area	169.594 m ²
	Miscellaneous losses	3%
Inverter	Efficiency	97%
	Capacity	28000
	Miscellaneous losses	1%
Summary	Capacity factor	17.7%
	Initial costs	47430000 CAD
	O&M	364000 CAD
	Electricity exported to grid	43537 mWh

Financial results from RETScreen expert application (Table 6) are quite different from the Excel scenario seen in Table 2 Annual costs are different because in Excel spreadsheet, debt term and debt ratio are not recognized. In RETScreen Expert the NPV result is greater, and Payback time is less, than the findings in Excel spreadsheet. Note that RETScreen expert referred to the SPP not DPP. In RETScreen, the LCOE is not clear, however according to other parameters provided in Table 6, LCOE can be calculated manually or in an Excel spreadsheet following Equation 3 above. The study found the LCOE from RETScreen outcomes were 1.9 BD Tk less than the result found in the Excel scenario. The difference in LCOE was once again governed by the difference in annual cost entries.

Table 6 Cost, Savings, Revenue and Financial Viability Results Calculated with RETScreen Expert

Cost/ Savings/ Revenue	
Total initial costs (100%)	47430000 CAD

O&M costs	364000 CAD
Debt payments-15years	1581000 CAD
Total Annual costs	1945000 CAD
Total annual savings and revenue	7310000 CAD
Net yearly cashflow-year1	5365000 CAD
Financial viability	
Net present value	37918651 CAD
Payback period	6.8
Equity payback period	4.1
IRR	11.6%
IRR for Equity	24.4%
Levelized Cost of Energy	0.09 CAD

4.4 Environmental impact assessment

To estimate the amount of CO₂ avoidance, we assume the power generated to replace electricity from imported fossil fuel in terms of crude oil. Although the Teknaf solar power plant had not yet closed its first year of operation, writers have discussed these factors since implicated in project papers, until commercial activities started. They made a common assumption for it to reduce more than the equivalent of 20000 tCO₂ [36]. Base case refers to tCO₂ equivalents when crude oil is the sole power source, and proposed case refers to tCO₂ equivalents sources from the Teknaf power plant. Teknaf solar power project contributes significantly to reducing the carbon footprint. The current study showed that only 7% of the base case are emitted (Figure 2). The power plant makes a 93% reduction of the base GHG emission, and saves the environment from 24533.9 tCO₂, which is equivalent to 57055.6 barrels of crude oil. The results on GHG emission reduction, spurs the cost effectiveness. In this scenario, we might conclude that additional revenues from sales of carbon credits can be an important source of profit for the producer, though it does not provide a significant increase to the NPV.

Figure 2 GHG emission reduction of the solar power plant in terms of annual tCO₂ emitted.

4.5 Risk analysis

This paper emphasized the assessment of underlying uncertainty of a new project’s costs and power generation and the uncertainty of projected cash flows. In RETScreen Expert, the project likelihood was performed on NPV with 5 input parameters (initial costs, operation & maintenance, electricity exported to the grid, debt ratio and debt term). All parameters have a risk range of ±25%. Resulting outcomes from risk analysis illustrated in (Table 7), and parameters input on the graph, show their relative impact on NPV. This was to assess the variability of data through standard deviation and variance; therefore, NPV outcomes are summarized on a distribution graph showing the central tendency such as the mean and median (Table 8, Figure 3).

Table 7 Risk analysis (RETScreen Expert)

Perform analysis on Net Present Value (NPV)					
Number of combinations (1000)					
Parameter	Unit	Value	Range (+/-)	Minimum	Maximum
Initial costs	\$	47430000	25%	35572500	59287500
O&M	\$	364000	25%	273000	455000
Electricity exported to grid	MWh	43537.18	25%	32652.88	544221.47
Debt ratio	%	50%	25%	37.5%	62.5%
Debt term	Year	15	25%	11	19

Table 8 NPV and risk level (RETScreen Expert)

Median	\$	37733704 CAD
Level of risk	%	10%
Minimum within level of confidence	\$	32361594 CAD
Maximum within level of confidence	\$	42808761 CAD

Figure 3 NPV Risk Analysis - Statistical distribution (RETSscreen Expert)

4.6 Sensitivity Analysis

We employed sensitivity analysis in this work to define the most important variable for the project's NPV, DPP, IRR and LCOE. All relevant parameters are changed by $\pm 25\%$ interval regarding their base values in both scenarios (Excel and RETScreen Expert). The study accounts for variables that greatly influence the NPV rather than for other tools. As NPV increases, optimum electricity production and the quicker payback period is approached, and LCOE decreases with less cost which also implies a greater IRR. Therefore, sensitivity analysis is performed on NPV. NPV values were defined from the software adjustment functions in which the simulations were performed. When one refers to Table 9 and Table 11 from Excel analysis and RETScreen Expert, and Figure 4 and Figure 6, it is interesting to note that the most significant variables for renewable power projects are 1) - the amount of electricity produced and 2) - initial investment. Other variables and factors (Capacity factor, discount rate) that are subjected to these two variables or their results may influence the project, but to a lesser degree. Sensitivity analysis in Table 10 and Figure 5, indicate that the bank loan plays an important role in the results of the cash flow analysis for a power project as both debt term and debt ratio contribute to the NPV growth. Remarkably,

debt ratio is more sensitive than the debt term since it causes fluctuations to the initial cost when it undergoes any change. As both the initial cost and operation costs & maintenance cost increase, the NPV decreases.

Table 9 Costs sensitivity on NPV value ($\pm 25\%$) calculated in Excel Spreadsheet

	-25%	-12.50%	0.00%	12.5%	25%
Initial cost	\$ 27,834,278.22	\$ 21,905,628.22	\$ 15,976,878.22	\$ 10,048,128.22	\$ 4,119,378.22
O&M cost	\$ 16,807,575.87	\$ 16,392,227.05	\$ 15,976,878.22	\$ 15,561,529.39	\$ 15,146,180.56
Electricity produced	\$ (705,538.99)	\$ 7,635,669.61	\$ 15,976,878.22	\$ 24,318,086.82	\$ 32,659,295.43

Figure 4 Costs sensitivity on NPV value ($\pm 25\%$): Excel Spreadsheet

Table 10 Debt ratio and debt term sensitivity on NPV value ($\pm 25\%$) (Excel scenario)

	-25%	-12.50%	0.00%	12.5%	25%
Debt term	\$ 25,020,506.04	\$ 26,034,037.71	\$ 26,947,929.81	\$ 27,773,512.46	\$ 28,520,721.80
Debt ratio	\$ 24,205,166.91	\$ 25,576,548.36	\$ 26,947,929.81	\$ 28,319,311.26	\$ 29,690,692.71

Figure 5 Debt ratio and debt term sensitivity on NPV ($\pm 25\%$ value RETScreen Expert)

Table 11 Costs sensitivity on NPV value ($\pm 25\%$; RETScreen Expert)

	-25%	-12.50%	0.00%	12.5%	25%
Initial cost	\$ 32,876,679.81	\$ 29,912,304.81	\$ 26,947,929.81	\$ 23,983,554.81	\$ 21,019,179.81
O&M cost	\$ 27,778,627.47	\$ 27,363,278.64	\$ 26,947,929.81	\$ 26,532,580.98	\$ 26,117,232.15
Electricity produced	\$ 10,265,512.60	\$ 18,606,721.20	\$ 26,947,929.81	\$ 35,289,138.41	\$ 43,630,347.02
Debt term	\$ 25,020,506.04	\$ 26,034,037.71	\$ 26,947,929.81	\$ 27,773,512.46	\$ 28,520,721.80
Debt ratio	\$ 24,205,166.91	\$ 25,576,548.36	\$ 26,947,929.81	\$ 28,319,311.26	\$ 29,690,692.71

Figure 6 Costs sensitivity on NPV value with 5 Variables ($\pm 25\%$): RETScreen Expert

5. Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to propose a framework that combines basic economic tools to assess investment attractiveness of renewable technologies. Through calculations of NPV, DPP, IRR and LCOE, the proposed methodology is capable of incorporating generation uncertainties and investment attractiveness of a power generation project based on renewable energies. Excel spreadsheet and RETScreen Expert were adopted for data treatment and simulation. In RETScreen Expert, energy produced was found to be affected by changes made on PV tilt angle and capacity factor, which justifies effects from climate and geographical conditions on renewable energy production. Optimization of tilt angle and maximization of capacity factors optimize power generation from renewable technologies. The increase in NPV is the result of cumulative present value of expected future cash flows using a discount rate provided in RETScreen Expert (9%), without accounting for taxes. To determine the amount of time it would take for the money invested in the project to be paid, or when the investor will start counting cash flow as interest from their investment, the study used the DPP approach. The value of IRR obtained is greater than the set benchmark rate of return (R) of the project ($IRR \geq R$). It indicates that the rate of return of the project has reached or exceeded the level of the set discount rate. These exact facts should push investors to examine the production cost to compare with the usual grid price or any other power generation system affordable to the society. The results of LCOE determined the socio-economical profitability and level of comparison of the solar power plant. An increase of costs to a fixed production amount might result in LCOE being greater for the grid price or unaffordable to society. LCOE drives the pricing decision that would govern the revenues. Risk and sensitivity analysis from both software indicated that the project possess a high probability of economic feasibility, especially when considering bank loans. Sensitivity and a risk range of ($\pm 25\%$), analysis applied on all independent variables against NPV, illustrates that the Teknaf solar power project can be a benchmark to implement other projects outlined in papers, especially due to doubts on investment attractiveness. Manifestation of the degree of attractiveness will encourage and increase confidence of the capacity expansion planner, and boost the will of shareholding from big investors to small investors.

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Conflicts of Interest

We, the authors, declared no conflicts of interest in this paper

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